

A DIGITAL CHEST OF DRAWERS FOR EXPLOSION DUST TO SUPPORT FORENSIC ANALYSIS

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INTRODUCTION

As part of the PyroProf project the Netherlands Forensic Institute (NFI) is collecting a large amount of data in relation to (an)ion concentrations over the Netherlands. The NFI is storing this data in .xlsx files on the local hard drive. With the current system, the NFI fails to make optimal use of the spatial aspect of the data; a program like Excel from Microsoft Office is not able to properly visualize the data using both the spatial and relational component of it.

For the PyroProf project the NFI obtains data through measurements executed by volunteers. Metadata about the measurements is obtained from a form, filled in by the volunteers, which contains information about the location, the sample object and the weather conditions of the sample. The forms are subsequently checked by the NFI and stored within several .xlsx files.

1.1 THE ASSIGNMENT

For improvement of capabilities in interpreting and sharing data, the commissioners have come to the understanding that the full potential of the spatial component of this data should be used. An environment or application built upon the spatial characteristics of the dataset would meet this requirement. So, the main goal of the NFI became to obtain an environment in which spatial referenced data can be organizedly stored, obtained and which is user-friendly for all employees of the team Explosions and Explosives of the NFI.

1.2 REQUIREMENTS OF THE NFI

The commissioners together have drawn up a set of requirements that had to be taken into account during the project. First of all, the importance of an interactive map wherein the gained data from the PyroProf project could be visualized. The data con-

tains information about; (i) concentration of the (an) ions, (ii) coordinates, (iii) date/time, (iv) the object whereon the measurement is taken, (v) the weather and (vi) an ID. For the Graphical User Interface (GUI) it was important that a map of the whole Netherlands would be visible with the data in it. All the (an)ions have to be implemented individually. It should be possible to click on the points, which are related to the (an)ions. Each point should contain the information mentioned above. The concentration of the ions should be visualized with a set of ranging colors.

The second requirement states that the application should be user-friendly. As the employees of the NFI lack experience with working in a GIS environment, like ArcGIS or QGIS, preference goes out to a simple new application. It would take a lot of time and investment before the employees would know how the software works, so a user-friendly custom made GUI might be a good alternative.

1.3 THE APPLICATION

In order to tackle the issue the NFI is currently dealing with, the team decided to develop a user-friendly web application, meeting the requirements identified by the commissioners themselves. The web application would include an interactive map and a data explorer. The final application is developed with the Shiny package and can be used within RStudio. The script should be able to read the data of the NFI, after they uploaded this to the database. By using clear documentation within the script, the script should become understandable for not experienced R users.

BACKGROUND

In order to gain more insight into the commissioners and their assignment, some brief background information on the institute and the PyroProf project is given in this chapter.

2.1 THE INSTITUTE

The Netherlands Forensic Institute (NFI) is an independent forensic organisation that provides reliable forensic information to organisations dealing with pursuit of peace, justice, and security - e.g. judiciary, Public Prosecution Service and the police - (NFI, 2018). Within the NFI, the Team Explosions and Explosives investigates whether an explosion occurred due to explosives or not. In order to do so, analysis of chemical composition of the chemical substances in the area where an explosion has occurred is carried out - see figure 1. Many of the ions present in inorganic explosives are also common in the environment. Therefore, the presence and concentration of those ions in evidence related to an explosion event needs to be compared with reference and background data in order to gather information about the type of explosive that caused the explosion (Lahoda et al., 2008).

2.2 THE PYROPROF PROJECT

Currently, the Dutch government wishes to improve the chemical profiling of inorganic and pyrotechnic explosives with the PyroProf project, funded by European Union. The NFI took up responsibility for this project and is now conducting a part of this research with the objective of obtaining more knowledge about the background concentrations of a group of ions, which naturally occur in the environment in the Netherlands (European Commission, 2017). This data will be sampled at 200 locations: city centres, agglomerations, rural areas, soils and around hot-spots - locations where explosions are more likely to occur or locations where the concentrations of ions is expected to be high-, such as Schiphol airport and governmental buildings of the Netherlands. In the future, more information will be collected from other locations, which could ultimately lead to the creation of a large dataset with background concentrations of explosion related ions in the Netherlands.

Figure 1 - Essential datasets for research on explosive events.

METHODOLOGY

In order to design a web application with relevant functionality for the NFI, several tasks needed to be executed. Those tasks can roughly be divided into (i) the organization of the data in a proper relational database and (ii) writing an application in R.

3.1 USABILITY STRATEGY

Given the fact that the commissioner emphasized the importance of a user friendly application, a usability strategy was defined. The usability strategy sets the method that is used to create a product in line with the requirements and expectations of the user in relation with the usability of this product. Usability is understood as how easy user interfaces is to use and to learn and the visualization style of the application.

Three meetings were scheduled with the commissioner in the usability strategy:

1. Requirements meeting; requirements for the products were discussed.
2. Intermediate results meeting; a prototype was presented by the project team and evaluated by the commissioner - during this meeting improvements and changes to the products have been discussed.
3. Final evaluation meeting; the final product is a working application and the user takes notes on features that work well and features that can improve while using the product. The notes are then shared and discussed in order to decide upon further improvements and additions.

Several style guides for the R script, Shiny application and SQL database are consulted for ensuring consistency and clearness during the whole project. In relation to consistency and clearness the Google's

R style guide describes some of the most important points of attention during scripting. These are; (i) awareness on notation and naming, (ii) consistent use of notation and naming, (iii) logical structuring of the script and (iv) clear documentary of the script (Google Open Source, 2018). Hadley Wickham made an adjustment on the Google's R style guide, stating that the documentary should be about the 'why' and not the 'what' (Wickham, 2018). Using a clear style guide ensures that the script will be re-usable and can be extended to other purposes (Johnson, 2018). Simon Holywell and Jonathon Hill developed also the same kind style guide for SQL databases. Consistency and documenting during the whole process are the main aspects (Holywell, 2015) (Hill, 2009).

From the requirement and intermediate meetings it was concluded that the NFI wishes to have an easy click application to see the sample information and concentration of ions in different areas. The focus of this application lies in visualizing the points and areas, selection on all the parameters of interest, and simplicity in design.

The NFI is interested in visualization of provinces, police districts and units, COROP areas, municipalities and the Netherlands as a whole.

Additionally, the ability to select on ions, sample objects, sample type, date and confidentiality is wished for. The sample types are divided into environmental survey samples, case study reference samples and case study post blast samples. Confidentiality also has set categories as well; non-confidential normal, non-confidential hotspot and confidential hotspot. In the future, categorizing the data on confidentiality should avoid potential data leaks when an adjusted version of this application will be used by police units

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as well. The ions, sample objects and data need to be adaptable based on future datasets, as the ion, sample objects and data need to be able to expand than the future.

They also wish that all information given is visible in the application as well, including weather information, object description and additional information.

To make sure that the application is simple and easy to understand, it is decided to have different tabs in the application with more detailed information on how the application works as well as a tab with a data table.

3.2 MYSQL DATABASE

After a meeting with the NFI and getting familiar with the workflow and activities of the team Explosions and Explosives, the first step of the project consisted of exploring the dummy data that was provided to the team by the commissioners. As in the future the amount and type of data records that need to be stored will increase, soon became evident that storing the data in a relational database management system (RDBMS) - which can be created, consulted, managed and maintained using the standardized language of SQL - would restrict both the future duplication of data and errors in the data processing to a minimum.

MySQL is an often used management system for relational databases. The SQL language is used to build, query and maintain the database. Data stored can be numbers, text, images and Binary Large Objects (BLOB). For this project, a database was created using MySQL Workbench. The relational data is graphically captured in a data model (see figure 2).

In order to access the data from the newly created database in the R script for the application, a connection is made to the database using the 'RMySQL' package, which allows for using SQL queries 'asking' for specific values from the tables in the database.

Currently the dataset is imported as two separate 'table views' - results of queries which are implemented in the script on the database. The first one contains the main values relating to each sample; the ID, ion concentrations, coordinates, sample object, sample type, sample date and confidentiality. The other table view contains additional information that is shown in the panel after the click interaction; o.a. weather conditions and more detailed information on the sample object and conditions.

3.3 R SCRIPTING USING SHINY

A Shiny app is an interactive web application build with the shiny package in R. It consists of 3 main parts: a User Interface (UI), a server and a global script. In the UI the interface is built where all interactions with the system are possible, a server script which defines the reactions of the system based on the interactions and a global script where the datasets and global values are defined. Details for how the application was created are given in the acceptance test (see annex 1).

The scripting starts in the global script. Here the databases are queried and data is prepared for the rest of the application. First, all data has to be merged into one large dataset called alldata, using the structure that benefits the application. Then the structure of the data is modified, by putting the ions in columns rather than rows. This significantly reduces the size of the dataset and provides a more efficient data visualization. Shapefiles for the different areas

of interest also need to be imported which also is done in global. As a structural choice, all functions used in server and UI were put into global as well.

The UI sets up the interface. In this script all interactive buttons and tabs as well as the design are defined. Customizability for different elements is significantly limited in R. However, interaction with css is possible which provides more customizability options, and for this, a separate style.css file is used.

Finally, the server gives function to the UI and the datasets. This is done by using observe statements, giving interaction within the buttons, and render statements, which provide content for tables and plots defined in the UI.

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Figure 2 - Database Model, built for this project using MySQL Workspace.

RESULTS

In the application, the data from the database can be visualized. Multiple buttons allow for specification of the users' search. The application can show the data based on 6 different region categories; (i) the whole Netherlands, (ii) provinces, (iii) municipalities, (iv) police units, (v) police districts and (vi) COROP regions. Not only in the interactive map, these differences are shown, but also in the data explorer categorisation on these region types is possible. After defining a specific region type, it is possible to select the (an)ions that preferred to be shown in the map. It is possible to select multiple (an)ions at the same time. Additionally, a time range can be selected. As a result, only the measurements within this particular range of dates are shown. Furthermore, the sample type (background, post blast and reference) and the object where the measurement is taken can be used to select upon.

After defining the right variables for the data which has to be visualized in the interactive map some measurements of the (an)ions will appear. It is possible to interact with the map by clicking on the measurements. In the right toolbar information about that specific measurement will appear.

The data explorer is the second item of the application. The structure of the data explorer consists of tables - with columns and rows. In the data explorer the possibility is offered to select your data based on the region types. Per measurements, the concentration of every ion can be seen. If the ID of the measurement is already known it is possible to search for that measurement by entering the ID in the search box. If all the wanted data is displayed in the data explorer, it is possible to download the table as .csv file.

More information about the application can be found in the following tabs; (i) about the application, (ii) extra information and (iii) the manual. About the application gives more background information about where the data is coming from and when was the last time the application is been updated. The extra information contains background information about the progress of the development of the shiny application. The manual explains how the application works.

The script is documented and explained in further detail in the acceptance test (see Annex I).

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Figure 3 - A printscreen of the final web application created for this project.

DISCUSSION

Currently the application has a visually appealing interface where different areas can be selected as well as parameters of interest. The data can be added with ease and can be downloaded from the application.

Naturally, the Shiny application can grow and develop with the needs of the NFI Explosions and Explosives team. For example, there was mention of locking the confidentiality for the police departments, which is not yet applicable. Furthermore, everything is currently built with the current dataset in mind, and future changes will require the application and the script to adapt.

As the data is now stored in a relational database, more complex queries can be executed to query the database for more analytical information. The queries can be implemented in the script, making it possible to enrich the application with more meaningful and relevant information.

The database created during this project should be managed and maintained; especially as more data will be added in the future.

With the .bat file in the application folder it is possible to start the application on your computer without having to open an R script. The application will then open as a web page. In our own opinion the application is developed according to the requirements of the NFI, so, overall, the goal of the ACT project is accomplished. By using clear tabs and buttons in the toolbar, the application should be easy to use for every user. The design is developed with the usage of high contrast colours, which ensures that the text in the application is clearly readable. By using the corporate identity and the logos of the NFI, it is

clear that the application is made for the NFI.

The data can be easily added to the application by putting it into excel and linking it to the database. By means of the download button in the data explorer app, it is also possible to retrieve the selected data from the application as a .csv file. Selections within the data can be made by region type, (an)ion, date and on what type of object the measurement was taken. The selections that are made in the panel of the tab of the interactive map can be seen immediately in the interactive map. All the data is not only visible in the interactive map, but also a graph view, text view and table view is added to the application. For making the application even more user friendly a guide tab is added to the application, wherein a description of how to make use of the application can be found.

Due to the limited time that was given for the ACT project the team was not able to also include some more in-depth analytic features. Features such as locking the confidentiality for police units or detailed analysis of explosives. Another point on the functional part of the application is that some aspects in the application should become more automated, e.g. the regions styles are now predefined in the R script.

Another aspect that can be improved upon is the design of the application. On the data explorer the data table is even wider than the windows even in full screen as it contains over 30 columns. A smaller data table, which would fit within the window size would be more user friendly. When using the application in a small window some of the logos are overlapping and get behind the title, which makes it harder to read, changes on the css file would be

needed in order to avoid this from happening. The last point of attention related to the design of the application is that the textual tabs are not designed and do not have a particular layout, adding a customized design for this tabs would make the application more visually appealing.

ADVICE

6.1 RESPONSIBILITY

It should be taken into account that there will be several roles regarding the application; (i) end user of the application, (ii) the database manager and (iii) the application manager.

End user

It is expected that the team Explosions and Explosives is the end user of the Application (possibly also police departments in the future).

Database manager

The database manager is responsible for managing and maintain the database that will be used for running the application. So the database manager will mainly be involved with keeping the the MySQL database optimized, information about the use of the database can be found in the Application Manual (Annex 2).The database should be managed by the team Explosions and Explosives, as they are responsible for the quality of the data and the input hereof.

Application manager

Finally, the application manager will work the most with the R script wherein the shiny application is developed. If any changes are planned for the script the application manager will implement these within the R script. The NFI IT department is expected to act as the application manager after this project, making sure the script further develops to the team Explosions and Explosives needs, update the script when packages are updated and possible errors. The IT department is also responsible for the installation of the application on the network/computers of the NFI.

Figure 4 - The different actors involved with the application.

6.2 FURTHER DEVELOPMENT

Now that this project is finished, the following is recommended for the application manager to further develop:

Actions

- Automatize object selection and column selection for the graphical output and make the ion selection more time efficient
- Fix additional information and graphical output crash while in browser mode
- Add images from the sample object in the database and in the table with Extra Information in the application
- Customize the calendar pop up from the date range to a more convenient location
- Reduce width of data table in order to make it fit into the window

- Disable the possibility of logo overlap when viewing the application in a small window

Research

- Pop ups with the click interactions; now all information about the selected samples is shown in the selection panel.
- Add a search bar where features (keywords) from the application can be written, and it provides an explanation of what it does and how it should be used.
- Add an action button in the table from the data explorer that, when clicked, takes you to the interactive map tab zoomed in to the selected location
- The possibility to select data in graph by using the datainbounds function present in the code.

A part of the goal from the NFI was to automate the addition of new objects in the application, which in the end was not possible within this time. It would likely require a loop like the ion automatization did. However, the ion automatization is already time intensive as well. Therefore, new ideas need to be tested to automate this selection.

The graphical output based on column selection is not automatized and should be adapted. This could probably be done by using the ions variable defined in the global.R. The current graph is also not functional within browser mode nor is the extra information button. This seems related to the shinyBS package, which is not supported in new versions of Shiny. This has no influence in the script version and Internet Explorer, but crashes in other browsers.

Images in the additional information are not yet vis-

ible and not yet implemented. It would be best if these are directly visible in the "Extra Information" button.

The customization of the calendar pop up is important as of right now as it may interrupt with the data selection process. This can likely be fixed using css just as well as the logo overlap that is happening sometimes and the width of the data table.

A nice addition could be to add pop ups with additional information instead of being limited to the button that would show everything. Key information has to be picked for that and has to be discussed closely with the team Explosions and Explosives.

Interesting to research would be to find the potential of adding a search bar to the application. This could provide great opportunities as it would make the application even more user friendly.

Interaction between the data table and the interactive map might be good as well. A zoom to a selected row could be implemented or a zoom to the current area selected in the data table. This is likely possible with javascript.

Finally, to analyze areas with explosions specifically, it could be very interesting to also allow data selection in the graph for the current field of view. With this function it could be really easy to compare ion concentrations over an area in a post blast and a survey sample situation. This has been done in other Shiny applications, like the application that inspired our application, called SuperZip (Cheng, 2012).

6.3 ADVICE FOR THE ORGANIZATION

During this project, the group was able to get familiar with the organization of NFI and how it works on a data level. The NFI is currently not having standards for saving or developing data. This can make it difficult to work with applications that are based on an automatized processes as well when communicating data with colleagues. Therefore, it is recommended to develop data standards so that future applications can run smoothly and that communication of data is more clear.

Now that there is a database created for the NFI, the team of course advises them to make use of it because using a database has the advantages that you can share your data with all the users of the same database. Using the MySQL for Excel plug-in it is possible to easily transfer the data from an .xlsx file to the database and thus the application.

The data that the team got from the NFI was spread over a lot of files, which required a lot of manual transformation to put them into a spread file. This process could be automated with scripting, allowing the measurement data to be immediately transferred to excel. Data gathered by volunteers could be automated as well with the use of a phone application that can upload data into the system directly. Creating such an application might be time intensive at first, but would save a significant amount of time long term.

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ANNEX I - Acceptance test

The following tests can be run to reproduce the Shiny application resulting from this project. The tests are carried out following SQL statements, creating a relational data model in MySQL Workbench and a script written in R.

For the R script, all data importation and setting up of functions are done in global.R. The file ui.R only describes the layout and options of the application; in server.R the meaning and computations behind the buttons and options of ui.R are being defined. To run the R script Rstudio can be downloaded from <https://www.rstudio.com/>.

1. Test 1: Organizing the data in MySQL

Based on the provided dummy data by the NFI - which was existing of several Excel sheets - a relational data model was designed using MySQL Workbench. Subsequently, the Excel data was transferred manually into Excel sheets according to the organization of the tables this model. Thereafter, the data was exported to the MySQL tables by using the MySQL For Excel plugin. The making of the tables is given in the snippet below

```
CREATE TABLE Post_blast_sample(  
ID_pb_sample INT UNSIGNED NOT NULL AUTO_INCREMENT PRIMARY KEY,  
ID_expl INT UNSIGNED NOT NULL,  
lat_sample_location FLOAT(10) UNSIGNED NOT NULL,  
lon_sample_location FLOAT(10) UNSIGNED NOT NULL,  
ID_sample_object INT UNSIGNED NOT NULL,  
ID_sample_surface INT UNSIGNED NOT NULL,  
ID_sampler INT UNSIGNED NOT NULL,  
date_sample DATE NOT NULL,  
ID_confidelity INT UNSIGNED NOT NULL DEFAULT 1);
```

```
#DROP TABLE Post_blast_sample;
```

```
CREATE TABLE Post_blast_concentration(  
ID_pb_sample INT UNSIGNED NOT NULL,  
ID_ion INT UNSIGNED NOT NULL,  
concentration VARCHAR(20));
```

```
#DROP TABLE Post_blast_concentration;
```

2. Test 2: Importing and using all datasets (global.R)

Before the shiny application can be set up, necessary preparations have to be done in the global.R

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script.

2.1. Step 1: Importing the data

In order to make a connection to the MySQL database in the R script for the Shiny application, the package called 'RMySQL' was installed. Within this package, it is possible to use SQL queries query for specific values from the tables - and that way making the data in the MySQL database accessible and ready for use using the R script. The importing is done for the three different sample types (survey, post blast and reference samples) and for key data and panel data; this results in a total of six imports. This is separated as mySQL had trouble creating one large data table. This datatable is therefore made in R instead.

```
postblast = dbGetQuery(mydb,
  `SELECT ID_expl, post_blast_concentration.ID_pb_sample,
  concentration, name_ion, post_blast_sample.ID_confidelity, type_object,
  lat_sample_location, lon_sample_location, post_blast_sample.date_sample
  FROM post_blast_concentration, post_blast_sample, ion, sample_object
  WHERE post_blast_sample.ID_pb_sample=post_blast_concentration.ID_pb_sample
  AND ion.ID_ion = post_blast_concentration.ID_ion
  AND post_blast_sample.ID_sample_object = sample_object.ID_sample_object;`)
```

2.2. Step 2: Combining the datasets

The different datasets have to be made into one and this is done with three actions. First two smaller datasets are made that have the same columns, so the key data and the panel data are combined using rbind(). To make sure this is possible, the smaller datasets are all given an uniqueID and identical names for their columns before being binded.

The second action consists of defining a link ID to combine the panel and key data, changing the concentrations to numeric data and renaming the confidentiality from numbers to named categories. For the concentrations it is in this case important to keep in mind that the Dutch version of excel uses commas as a decimal point unlike English systems like R who use a dot. Therefore, extra code has to be implemented to fix this issue:

```
binded$concentration=as.numeric(gsub(",", "\.", gsub("\\.", "", binded$concentration)))
```

The third action is the most important one as it combines both datasets and sets all ions as columns rather than rows. This makes the dataset smaller and more efficient for visualization. In order to do this, the uniqueID created in the binded dataset is put in a "for" loop and a selection of data with that uniqueID is made and all data is selected from that. Each uniqueID has only one value for each attrib-

ute with the exception of ions. Therefore, ions are put in an additional “for” loop to add all unique ions in the columns created for the alldata dataset. The panel data and key data are combined here using the linkID.

```
alldata = data.frame()

for(i in 1:length(unique(binded$uniqueID))){
  alldata[i,"uqID"] = unique(binded$uniqueID)[i]
  datapart = binded[binded$uniqueID==alldata$uqID[i],]
  datapart_panel = panel_bind[panel_bind$linkID == datapart$linkID[1],]
  alldata[i,"lon_sample"] = datapart$lon_sample_location[1]
  alldata[i,"lat_sample"] = datapart$lat_sample_location[1]
  alldata[i,"s_conf"] = datapart$ID_confidelity[1]
  alldata[i,"date"] = datapart$date_sample[1]
  alldata[i,"s_object"] = datapart$type_object[1]
  alldata[i,"s_type"] = datapart$s_type[1]
  alldata[i,"d_object"] = datapart_panel$descr_object[1]
  alldata[i,"weather"] = datapart_panel$category_weather[1]
  alldata[i,"xtra_info"] = datapart_panel$additional_info[1]
  for(j in 1:length(ions)){
    if(ions[j] %in% datapart$name_ion){
      alldata[i,ions[j]] = datapart$concentration[datapart$name_ion==ions[j]]
    } else {
      alldata[i,ions[j]] = 0
    }
  }
}
```

2.3. Step 3: Setting up selection options

The selection options used in the UI file need to be defined and these are given in the data for the most part. The sample type and confidentiality are defined manually in order to give more proper names in the selection. This lack of automatization should hold no issue as these categories are not expected to change. The ion and the object options are automatized easily with the snippets below.

```
object <- unique(binded$type_object)
ions <- unique(binded$name_ion)
```

2.4. Step 4: Importing shapefiles

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The different shapefiles used to define the area options are saved in the datafile. This makes importing them easier and more consistent. The only changes that are made in the shapefiles is a column name, which is changed to obtain more consistent naming and the coordinates, which are set to the same system the point data is in.

```
police_districts_shp <- readOGR(dsn = "./data/Shapefiles/PoliceDistricts.shp")
police_districts_shp <- police_districts_shp[order(police_districts_shp$DISTR_NAAM), ]
police_districts_shp@data <- dplyr::rename(police_districts_shp@data,
"name" = "DISTR_NAAM")
police_districts_shp <- spTransform(police_districts_shp, CRS=prj_string_WGS)
```

2.5. Step 5: Providing regional information to the data:

To be able to select based on location, it is useful to give the data regional information. To achieve this, an overlay between the shapefiles and the spatial data points (alldata) is carried out with the function `over(alldata, police_districts_shp)`. This function returns the names of the regions for each location defined in alldata, if no overlay, it returns NA. The information from both the overlay is then combined using `cbind()` with alldata to include regional data in alldata. Sometimes, the shapefiles contain additional information that has to be removed. To remove a column its content is set to NULL (f. ex. `region_data_points$FTE <- NULL`).

3. Test 3: Creating the interface (UI)

In the UI the interface is built which makes all interactions with the system possible. This is a key part, as this will define the way that the end user experiences the application. This test explains how this interface can be set up.

3.1 Step 1: Build the User Interface

The User Interface was created with Shiny using the function `ui <- fluidpage()`. The script containing the code to create the UI is called `ui.R`. Inside the `fluidpage` the user interface is structured. To start with, a `shinytheme` can be added using `theme = shinytheme`. A `shinytheme` is a bootstrap css file that provides a default visualization style to the application. For this project, the theme `superhero` was used.

A title was set by means of the function `titlePanel()`. Inside the title panel 3 logos were included. In order to include the logos, html code was used. To introduce html code in the R script, the code is written inside a `div()`. The following code shows how the title Panel was constructed in the application:

```
ui <- shinyUI(fluidPage(theme = shinytheme("superhero"),
titlePanel(
title= div(class= "titlepanel", div(id= "imgEU",
```

```
img(src="European_Commission.svg",
width= "30%", height= "15%", style="float:right;", align = "center")),
div(id = "imgPyroProf", img(src = "Pyrprof-logo-trans-grey.png",
width = "10%", height= "10%", style = "float:right", align= "center" )),
div(id = "imgNFI", img(src="logo-nfi-white.png",
width= "60%", height= "60%", style="float:right;")),
div( id = "title", "Ion concentrations in relation to explosive substances"), "PyroProfApp"),
```

The images are named as the scr, and located in a folder called www. The exact position of the images is set in a custom style.css file. This file is added to the shiny app with the following code:

```
tags$head(includeCSS("styles.css"))
```

A navigation bar was included with navbar(). Inside of navbar the different tabs can be created with the function tabPanel(). Four tabs were created for this application.

The first tab shows a leaflet map, with the height and width set as percentages. The tab contains a panel created by absolutePanel(), which includes buttons that can be used to interact with the content of the map. In this panel, data from a clicked point in the map can also be seen. In the second tab, a table with the data from the points of the map can be seen. Furthermore, data that is included can be selected for regions, and downloaded. A third and a fourth tab were included, containing only text and links.

The following functions were used in this application to include buttons, tables and other features:

selectInput (): Create a select list that can be used to choose a single or multiple items from a list of values. This dropdown can be typed into to select as well.

uiOutput (): Render a reactive output variable as HTML within an application page. Used in this application to show a list to select from dependant on the selected item of a selectInput.

dateRangeInput (): Creates a pair of text inputs which, when clicked on, bring up calendars that the user can click on to select dates.

leafletOutput (): Creates a container for the leaflet map.

dataTableOutput(): Creates a container for an interactive table built with the package DT.

tableOutput (): Creates a container for a table.

dropdownButton(): Button defined by a function in global.R which contains checkboxes to select from.

checkboxGroupInput (): Creates a group of checkboxes that can be used to toggle multiple choices independently.

bsModal(): Creates a modal window, which is a popup window that is displayed on top of the current page. The modal window is triggered by an action (like clicking a button), and can display text, plots,

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tables.

`actionButton()`: Creates an action button, which is a button that triggers an action when it is clicked.

`downloadButton ()`: Creates a download button or link which, when clicked, initiates a browser download. It is defined as an html function in `global.R`. This is possible because even though a drop-down button does not exist in Shiny, it does in html, and html code can be used to write and include features and items to a Shiny app.

3.2. Step 2: Write custom cascading style sheet (CSS)

A CSS is a style sheet language used for describing how the elements should of a document written in html and other markup languages should be displayed. Every item in the application has a class and/or and id, which either has been explicitly defined in the code or is given by Shiny as default. Classes are referred to as `.classname{}`, and ids as `#idname{}`. Shiny app uses a bootstrap-theme css, but the application can be further personalized by changing elements in a custom `style.css`. These items can be used in the css file to modify its visualization (position, size, shape, color, font, etc.). Css code can also be written inside the Rscript, but can be separate as well as given with the snippet below. The css file follows the same structure of the text that is between quotes.

```
tags$style(HTML(".multicol {  
  -webkit-column-count: 2; /* Chrome, Safari, Opera */  
  -moz-column-count: 2; /* Firefox */  
  column-count: 2;  
}"))
```

When the id and class that wants to be modified are defined by Shiny, elements of the application can be investigated by right clicking and pressing the inspect button. This will pop up a small window in which a large html code is given on the left and the css code on the right (see figure 2). Once holding your mouse on the different html codes on the left, different parts of the application will seem selected. Pick the one that you are interested in, and preferably one with a visible ID or class so that this can be easily edited. Changes can be made in the inspect window, which allows to find and test the items that have to be included or modified in the css file. However, changes in the inspect window are only temporary and will not be saved for the next run. Therefore the changed part needs to be copied and pasted in either the script or the css file.

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Visualization of the inspector tool

The main changes made in the css were in relation to the following:

The position of several buttons of the leaflet map (by setting position, right, and top / bottom).

For the measuring button, the color of the font was changed to black adding `color: black;` to the css code.

The position of the logos was set in a similar way.

The appearance of the background panel was set by giving it `background-color`.

The size of the dropdown buttons was changed to make them all the same size, the color was changed to match the style of the application, and the content inside the ions tab was aligned by setting width

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The position of the logos was set in a similar way.

The appearance of the background panel was set by giving it background-color.

The size of the dropdown buttons was changed to make them all the same size, the color was changed to match the style of the application, and the content inside the ions tab was aligned by setting width and margins to the checkbox.

Fonts were customized: a font family and font-weight was given as default for the application.

Colors from the data table were changed from the default colors, to make them more suitable to the style of the application, and sizes (height and width) of the boxes to input information were changed to make them equal.

4. Test 4: Setting up interaction with buttons

The final part of the script is the server.R which defines the action carried out when buttons are pressed, thus defining the interactions possible within the UI.

4.1. Step 1: Map functions and interactions (global.R)

The leaflet map was created as a function inside the global.R script. The default area is centered in the Netherlands, and several additional buttons were added to the map. Buttons that allow to reset the map view back to the Netherlands, to measure distances between points and to change the background layer of the map. For the most part the functionality is self explanatory, but for the different background layers these have to be added and defined as groups in the addTiles part of the function.

```
setmap <- function(input, output){
  observe(
    {
      output$map <- renderLeaflet({
        leaflet() %>%
          addTiles(group= "Map",
            urlTemplate = "//{s}.tiles.mapbox.com/v3/jcheng.map-5ebohr46/{z}/{x}/{y}.png",
            attribution = 'Maps by <a href="http://www.mapbox.com/">Mapbox</a>'
          )%>%
          addProviderTiles(group = "Satellite", 'Esri.WorldImagery'
          )%>%
          # Set zoom to the default longitude, latitude and zoom level
          setView(lng = avglng, lat = avglat, zoom = zoomlvl)%>%
```

```

    addResetMapButton()%>%
    addMeasure(position = "bottomleft", primaryLengthUnit = "meters", primaryAreaUnit = "sqme-
ters",
              activeColor = "#3D535D", completedColor = "#7D4479")%>%
    addLayersControl( position = "bottomleft", baseGroups = c("Map", "Satellite"),
                    options = layersControlOptions(collapsed = FALSE))
  })})}

```

Another key mapping function is the setpoints function which is used each time a selection is changed. First the current circles are cleared to avoid stacking points and then the circles and legend are defined.

```

setpoints = function(input, output){
  leafletProxy("map", data = seldata) %>%
  clearGroup(group = "circles") %>%
  addCircleMarkers(~lon, ~lat, layerId=~uqID, group = "circles",
                  stroke=T, color="black", weight=1, fillOpacity=0.8, fillColor=~col,label = ~uqID, radius
= 7) %>%
  addLegend("bottomleft", col = c("pink","darkred","lightskyblue",
                                "darkblue","limegreen","darkgreen"),
            labels=c("Postblast: 0-1 ppm","Postblast: >1 ppm","Reference: 0-1 ppm",
                    "Reference: >1 ppm","Survey: 0-1 ppm","Survey: >1 ppm"), title="Legend",
            layerId="colorLegend")}

```

All other map functions are similar or smaller parts of the function above. This function can be found in the global.R code to avoid crowding the server.R code with using this smaller part multiple times.

4.2. Step 2: Set adaptable buttons for the UI (Server.R)

There are two types of buttons that requires to observe UI activity, namely the area button and the select all buttons.

The area button responds to the input of the region. The choices within the area should all fall into the category of the region and this is done with a renderUI and an if statement in the choices for the areaselection. Despite this being set in the server, this input definition has the same functionality as the UI input definitions do.

```
output$areaselection <- renderUI({
```

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```
selectInput("area", "Area:",width = "100%", choices =
  if(input$a_type=="nl"){nl
  } else if(input$a_type == "prov"){prov
  } else if(input$a_type == "mun"){mun
  } else if(input$a_type == "polunit"){polunit
  } else if(input$a_type == "pd"){pd
  } else {COROP}})
```

The select all buttons need to update the checkbox inputs from the UI to either activate all or deactivate all. This is done with the snippet found below. This works the same for every select all functions.

```
observeEvent(input$all_si,{
  updateCheckboxGroupInput(
    session, `ions`, choices = ions,
    selected = if (input$all_si) ions,inline=F
  )
})
```

4.3. Step 3: Map selection (Server.R)

Upon selecting a type region, the areas are made visible, but also a zoom level is set once an area is selected. See snippet below. This zoomlvl is used for the setView function in both setmap and viewset.

```
observe(
  if(input$a_type == "mun"|input$a_type == "COROP"){zoomlvl<- 10
  } else if(input$a_type == "nl"){zoomlvl<- 7
  } else {zoomlvl<- 8}
)
```

Based on the areaselection, the map changes the zoom location and a polygon appears on the selected area. This is done by first selecting the correct coordinates from the relevant shapefiles imported in global.R, then an average is made for the zoom location and the coordinates are defined for the polygon.

```
observeEvent(input$a_type,{
  if(input$a_type == "prov"){area_type=provinces_shp
  } else if (input$a_type == "mun"){area_type=municipalities_shp
  } else if (input$a_type == "polunit"){area_type=police_units_shp
  } else if (input$a_type == "pd"){area_type=police_districts_shp
```

```

} else if (input$a_type == "COROP"){area_type=corop_region_shp
} else {return(NULL)}
lin <- as(area_type, "SpatialLinesDataFrame")
pts <- as.data.frame(as(lin, "SpatialPointsDataFrame"))
})

observeEvent(input$area,{
  if(input$area == "nl"){
    leafletProxy("map", data = seldata) %>% removeShape(layerId = "polygons")
    avglng <- 6
    avglat <- 52
  } else {
    coord1 <- pts$coords.x1[pts$name == input$area]
    coord2 <- pts$coords.x2[pts$name == input$area]
    avglng <- mean(coord1)
    avglat <- mean(coord2)
    setpolygon(input, output)
    setpoints(input, output)
  }
  viewset(input, output)
}
)

```

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4.4. Step 4: Selection on attributes (Server.R)

Selection is the most important part for the map visualization. Dates, ions, sample type, sample object and confidentiality can be selected on and interact with each other. Most of these have different selection methods and these are given in unique substeps.

4.4.1. Substep 4.1.: Selection on dates

The selection on dates is the simplest out of all the selections. This is done simply by checking whether the dates within alldata are smaller than the maximum date and larger than the minimum date.

```

observe({
  date_select <- alldata@data[(alldata$date >= input$dates[1] &
alldata$date <= input$dates[2]),]
  setseldata(input, output)
})

```

4.4.2. Substep 4.2.: Selection on confidentiality, type and objects

Sample type, confidentiality and sample objects work in similar ways. For them, the rows are selected based on the selected options. This method works excellent for confidentiality and sample type, however for objects it is not as efficient because currently there are many objects, and it is expected this will expand in the future. Consequently, It is recommended to find a way to fix this with a loop.

```
observe({
  env = type[1] ; ref = type[2] ; pb = type[3]
  type_select <- alldata[(env %in% input$s_type & env == alldata@data$s_type)|
    (ref %in% input$s_type & ref == alldata@data$s_type)|
    (pb %in% input$s_type & pb == alldata@data$s_type),]
  setseldata(input, output)
})
```

4.4.3. Substep 4.3.: Selection on ions and color definition

The ions are the most difficult to select on, because there are many of them, they are adaptable, and they need to be selected based on values rather than availability. Furthermore, the concentration of the ions define the meaning behind the colors on the map. This is done using two 'for' loops, one for every row and one for every ion column, making it possible to check every value for whether it is above 0. If any of the selected ions has a value above 0, it is added to the selection. This works the same way for detecting higher values during the color definition, where the check is done on a concentration of 1.

```
observeEvent(c(input$ions, input$all_si),{
  tempdata = alldata@data[0,]
  if(!is.null(input$ions)){
    for(j in 1:nrow(alldata@data)){
      max_val = 0
      for(i in 1:length(input$ions)){
        if(alldata@data[j,input$ions[i]] > 0){
          if(alldata@data[j,input$ions[i]] > max_val){
            max_val = alldata@data[j,input$ions[i]]
          }
        }
        if(nrow(tempdata)==0){
          tempdata[1,] = alldata@data[j,]
        } else if(!(alldata@data[j,1] %in% tempdata[,1])){
          tempdata[nrow(tempdata)+1,] = alldata@data[j,]
        }
      }
    }
  }
})
```

```

}
#define visible color
if(alldata$s_type[j]=="postblast"){
  alldata$col[j] <- ifelse(max_val > 1, "darkred", "pink")
} else if(alldata$s_type[j]=="reference"){
  alldata$col[j] <- ifelse(max_val > 1, "darkblue", "lightskyblue")
} else if(alldata$s_type[j]=="survey"){
  alldata$col[j] <- ifelse(max_val > 1, "darkgreen", "limegreen")
}
}
ion_select <- tempdata
} else {ion_select <- alldata@data[0,]}
setseldata(input, output)
}
)

```

4.4.4. Substep 4.4.: setseldata()

In order to have all selections interact, a function is set up called setseldata. The function is similar to substep 4.2. where it checks whether the rows of alldata are also in all selections. The seldata is then used for the addCircleMarkers in setpoints to show the results.

```

setseldata <- function(input, output){
  seldata <- alldata[(alldata$uqID %in% ion_select$uqID &
    alldata$uqID %in% obj_select$uqID &
    alldata$uqID %in% date_select$uqID &
    alldata$uqID %in% conf_select$uqID &
    alldata$uqID %in% type_select$uqID),]

  if(nrow(seldata@data)==0){
    clearpoints(input,output)
  } else {
    setpoints(input, output)
  }
}

```

4.5. Step 5: Setting up extra information graphics and table (Server.R)

In order to obtain information when a point is clicked in a map, the event (when the point is clicked) has to be observed. This clicked point has a unique id which is given in the leaflet function. In this ap-

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plication, the id corresponds to the uqID in seldata. Thus, this ID can be used to create a subset from seldata that only contains information about the point that has been clicked. Finally, data from this point can be converted to a data.frame class and can be used to define the output of the UI table and plot inside the functions renderUI and renderPlotly respectively. renderUI was used instead of renderTable because it was preferred to provide the table a customized look. The table was created in html, which allows to include a title for the table as a cell that takes several columns (colspan = 2), and to make the row names bold (tags\$b("rowname")).

```
tags$table(class = "table",
  tags$thead(tags$tr(
    tags$th (colspan = 2,"Sample Information")
  )),
  tags$tbody(
    tags$tr(
      tags$td(tags$b("ID")),
      tags$td(myData$uqID)),
    tags$tr(
      tags$td("Date"),
      ....
    )
  )
})
```

Inside renderPlotly, the data from the ions concentration were selected and used for the plot. Furthermore, plot size, title, margins, font were set to customize the plot to the needs of the application.

```
histogram <- plot_ly(histogrammdf, x = ~xhistogram, y = ~yhistogram, type='bar',
  marker = list(color = "rgb(37,84,165)")) %>%
  layout(annotations = a_title , margin = list(b=50, t = 25),
  xaxis = ax, yaxis = ay, width = 315, height = 220,
  font = list(family = "sans-serif", size = 8))
```

4.6. Step 6: Setting up the datatable tab (Server.R)

In the data explorer tab, there are two Input text, which contain information about Regions. The regions list that the user can select upon depends on the selected region type, because the choices are given by get(input\$a_type). input\$a_type is a name (mun for municipality, nl for Netherlands, etc.), and the same name, is given to a list containing all regions, for example mun contains all municipality names. Therefore, the result of get("mun") is a list with all municipalities.

In order to build the table, the data that contains information about location (region_data_points) is filtered by the selected region. If nl is selected, all data is shown, otherwise, a subset containing only the data from the selected region is shown. The table is then built with the function datatable() from the package DT. The exact same code is used for the Download button, so it downloads only the data from the selected region, but, instead of building a table, an excel file is created with the function write.csv().

```
output$explosionsdata <- DT::renderDataTable({
  # Set content of the table
  df <- region_data_points
  # Filter content on region selected
  df <- filter(df,
    input$regions == "nl" |
    is.null(input$regions) | input$regions == df$COROP |
    input$regions == df$municipality | input$regions == df$province |
    input$regions == df$police_units | input$regions == df$police_districts
  )

  df$X <- NULL
  df$col <- NULL
  df$date <- format(df$date, "%d-%m-%Y")
  # Build datatable with style from the given theme
  DT::datatable(df, style = "bootstrap", escape = FALSE)
})
```

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ANNEX II - Application manual

This document provides all information to make the application work on your own computer. It includes descriptions of the required software and the packages that are needed.

R

R is a programming language in which the application is written. The packages that will be used within the script are downloaded automatically. The application uses the following packages: leaflet, leaflet.extras, shiny, shinythemes, plotly, RColorBrewer, scales, lattice, plyr, dplyr, rgdal, DT, raster and RMySQL. R needs to be downloaded for all roles regarding the application: end users, database managers and application managers. Downloading R can be done through the following website and is completely free:

<https://cran.r-project.org/>

RSTUDIO

RStudio is a free and open-source integrated development environment for R. This environment needs to be downloaded by the database managers and the application managers. Download RStudio on this website:

<https://www.rstudio.com/products/rstudio/download/#download>

(The development team used version 3.4.3.)

MYSQL

MySQL is an open-source relational database management system (RDBMS). To make the database work, three elements are needed: MySQL Community Server, MySQL Workbench and the MySQL Plugin for Excel. MySQL also uses C++ and can be downloaded together with the other elements (it is a requirement to run) in the MySQL installer. MySQL needs to be downloaded for all roles regarding the application: end users, database managers and application managers. The system and all the elements can be downloaded for free via the following links:

<https://dev.mysql.com/downloads/installer/>

(The development team used version 5.7.22 for the MySQL Server, version 6.3.10 for the MySQL Workbench and version 1.3.7 for MySQL for Excel.)

HOW TO GET THE MYSQL DATABASE READY TO USE?

For getting a functional connection between the MySQL database and the application it is important to first make a connection with a local server within the MySQL workbench. This can be done by opening the MySQL workbench application. The application will appear and then it is possible to make a new connection to the local server. It is possible to set a password if wished for. It is possible to open the newly created connection by double clicking on it. You should get the same window as in figure 1 is

displayed.

Figure 1: MySQL Workbench interface.

In figure 2 two important buttons are marked for the next step. The first button (left) is the “Create a new schema” button. It is important to create a new schema with a proper name, which ensures more clearness for yourself when working with MySQL. The second button is the “Create a new query” button, which is needed for adding the CREATE_TABLES_query.txt (this file can be found in the “Database Files” folder) into it. Now it is possible to copy the text from the CREATE_TABLES_query.txt (this file can be found in the “Database Files” folder) into MySQL Workbench. It is important to double click on the newly created schema and run the query. This can be done by clicking on the lightning bolt icon above the query. After this is done you can refresh the “SCHEMAS” by clicking on the refresh button next to it.

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Figure 2: Buttons that need to be used to create a schema (right) and a query (left)

The next step is within Excel. Open the Data_tables.xlsx file and go to the "Gegevens"/"Data" tab. Open the MySQL for Excel plug-in. Select by double clicking the name of the newly created Local Connection for gaining access to this server. If an error containing "Authentication method 'caching_sha2_password' not supported by any of the available plugin." occurs, follow the next additional steps:

Executing the install file;

Select "Reconfigure" over the mysql server;

In Authentication Method tab, select "Use Legacy Authentication Method")

Enter the password if required. You will see a list of the tables now. If you don't; refresh the schema in the MySQL Workbench program. Double click on the schema that you have created. Select the data (NOT the headers, only the data) you want to add to the corresponding table in the MySQL database. Keeping this selection, click on the corresponding table in the MySQL For Excel plugin. Click on 'Append Excel Data to Tab' (The pop-up screen should show green colors for each column, if not; check if you selected the Excel columns correctly). Click on 'Append' in the pop-up screen. Repeat this for all Excel sheets.

Figure 3: Overview of the tables within the database

Figure 4: Overview of what dat a should look like

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Move the cursor to a table of interest; three icons will appear. Click on the most right icon to view what is in the table (a query, e.g. "SELECT * FROM Explosion;" will be runned). The data should then look like the data that is displayed in figure 4.

After everything is set well in the MySQL it is necessary to change the 'username', 'password', and 'dbname' in the global.R. See the following snippet what has to be changed.

```
#make connection with MySQL database (fill in: user, password, dbname, host=local)
killDbConnections <- function () {
  all_cons <- dbListConnections(MySQL())
  for(con in all_cons)
    + dbDisconnect(con)
}
killDbConnections()
mydb = dbConnect(MySQL(), user = 'username', password = 'password', dbname = 'database name',
host = 'localhost');
```

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HOW TO RUN THE APPLICATION?

There are two ways to run this application. The most ideal way would be to open the application by clicking on the "Application.bat" file, because in that case it is not necessary anymore to open RStudio. But unfortunately, there is a bug in the "Extra information" and "Expand chart" button when used with Google Chrome as a default browser. So, when running the .bat file, it is not possible to use those buttons in Google Chrome, but they do work within Internet Explorer.

Luckily it is possible to use the buttons when the application is running from RStudio. Running the application with RStudio can be done by first opening the "ApplicationMain.R"-script with Rstudio (double click on this script in the folder to open RStudio), and subsequently clicking on the "Run App" button. The "Run App" button can be found in the top-right of the script window (Figure 5). The application is now starting.


```
1 # Designing a GIS-system for the NFI: A digital chest of drawers for explosion dust to support for site analysis
2 # Authors: Luuk van Gorp, Fleur Jonker, Christopher Kurth, Jorn Neppelenbroek, Aina Tubau Comas
3 # Date: 3rd of July, 2018
4
5 # Load necessary packages, and install them if not already installed
6 if (!require(plyr)) {install.packages("plyr"); library(plyr)}
7 if (!require(dplyr)) {install.packages("dplyr"); library(dplyr)}
8 if (!require(rgdal)) {install.packages("rgdal"); library(rgdal)}
9 if (!require(DT)) {install.packages("DT"); library(DT)}
10 if (!require(raster)) {install.packages("raster"); library(raster)}
11 if (!require(leaflet)) {install.packages("leaflet"); library(leaflet)}
12 if (!require(leaflet.extras)) {install.packages("leaflet.extras"); library(leaflet.extras)}
13 if (!require(RMySQL)) {install.packages("RMySQL"); library(RMySQL)}
14 if (!require(shiny)) {install.packages("shiny"); library(shiny)}
15 if (!require(shinythemes)) {install.packages("shinythemes"); library(shinythemes)}
16 if (!require(plotly)) {install.packages("plotly"); library(plotly)}
17 if (!require(RColorBrewer)) {install.packages("RColorBrewer"); library(RColorBrewer)}
18 if (!require(scales)) {install.packages("scales"); library(scales)}
19 if (!require(lattice)) {install.packages("lattice"); library(lattice)}
20
21 #Read code from other (function) scripts
22 source("ui.R")
23
24 #Run the interactive tool application
25 runApp("ui.R")
26
27
28
29
30
31
--
```

Figure 5: The "Run App" button is positioned in the top-right of the script window.

Use of the application (Guide)

The guide provides a short guide for the application and can also be found in the "Guide" tab of the application. The application includes four tabs: "Interactive map", "Data explorer", "Guide" and "About", of which the first two are the most important ones.

1. Interactive tab

The interactive tab contains two main elements (main and side panel), which are described separately.

1.1 Main panel (map)

The main panel of this tab consists of the map on which the spatial information about samples/ions is displayed. The information on the map can be changed with the tools on the side panel, more information about this panel can be found in the next section.

The following elements/tools are included in the map:

- Sample dots: The dots that are visible in the map represent the locations where the samples have been taken. Information about the meaning of the color of the dots can be found in the legend. A graph will show up in the side bar, when clicking on one of the points. More information about the samples (day, comments, object type, etc.) can be found with the button "Extra information", as described in the next section.

Zoom in: Click on the button with the plus icon to zoom in (top left of the map).

Zoom out: To zoom out, use the button with the minus symbol (top left of the map).

Reset view: The button with four arrows (top left of the map) resets the view to the Netherlands.

Change basemap: The radio buttons (bottom left corner) allow to change the basemap, there are two options: a satellite image and the normal map.

Measurement tool: The tool with the ruler icon (next to the basemap radio buttons) can be used to measure distances and areas within the map.

Legend: The legend (bottom left corner) provides more information about the points that are visible in the map.

1.2 Side panel

The side panel can be found on the right part of the "Interactive map" tab. Within this panel it is possible to filter the information that is shown in the map.

The following elements are included in the side panel:

Type of region select box: This dropdown box allows the user to select a type of region. The options are: provinces, municipalities, police units, police districts and COROP regions, the default setting is the Netherlands. Options for the different regions are shown in the "area select box", after selecting one of the types.

Area select box: After choosing a type of region from the "type of region" select box, options will show up in the "area select box". After choosing one of the regions from the dropdown menu, an outline of

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that region will show up on the map and it will automatically zoom in to the chosen region.

Date range selector: With this tool it is possible to select a date range. When a certain range is selected, only samples that are taken within this time interval are shown in the map. The left box is for the start of the interval, the right box is for the end of the date interval. A date selector will pop up when clicking on the select box, on top of the select box one can navigate through months and years. Another possibility is to type in a date manually: click on the select box, remove the initial date and type in the date of choice (DD-MM-YYYY).

Sample type select box: This select box allows to filter the shown samples based on different sample types: Environmental sample survey, Case study: Reference and Case study: Post blast.

Ion select box: The sample dots in the map can be filtered with help of the "Ion select box". Click on the select box to get a list with the ions that are possibly present in the samples. After selecting the ions that you are interested in, only the samples that have concentrations greater than 0 ppm are shown in the map.

Sample object select box: Samples were taken on different kind of objects. This dropdown box provides the different object options and filters the shown samples based on the selected sample objects.

Confidentiality select box: This select box has three options: non-confidential, non-confidential hotspots and confidential hotspots. This select tool acts as a filter: when an option is selected, the shown sample dots on the map have that corresponding confidentiality.

Extra information button: A pop up will show a table with additional information about the sample after using the button. It can only be used when a point has been selected.

Expand chart button: This button allows the user to enlarge the chart with ion information. At the same time, more tools are enabled within the expansion window (e.g. download chart, zoom in, reset axis etc.). These tools can be found in the top of the graph and are well explained when hovering over the tools. Furthermore, when hovering over the bars in the chart, it shows the name of the ion and the corresponding value. This button can only be used when a point has been selected.

Chart [only visible in the side panel after a point has been selected]: This chart is a basic version of the chart in the expanded chart window (use "expand chart" button). When hovering over the bars in the chart, it shows the name of the ion and the corresponding value. This button can only be used when a point has been selected.

2. Data explorer tab

The data explorer tab contains a filter section and a section with a table, in which all information can be found about the samples, as stored in the database.

The following elements/tools are included in this tab:

2.1 Filter panel

Type of region select box: This dropdown box allows the user to select a type of region. The options

are: provinces, municipalities, police units, police districts and COROP regions, the default setting is the Netherlands. Options for the different regions are shown in the "area select box", after selecting Area select box: After choosing a type of region from the "type of region" select box, options will show up in the "area select box". After choosing one of the regions from the dropdown menu, only those regions are shown in the data table.

Download button: This button allows the user to download the data that is shown within the table as a CSV file.

2.2 Table panel

- Search bar: In this bar one can fill in a keyword/number/data/etc. to filter the data.

Data table: The data table provides all the information that is available for the (selected) samples. More information can be seen when scrolling to the right. Clicking on the column enables the user to sort the data differently (based on the clicked column). In the bottom you can find a panel to go to the next page of the table.

3. Guide tab

The "Guide" tab contains all the "Use of the application" information.

4. About tab

This tab includes a short background of the project and provides contact information.

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